

The Dancer, Her Dance & The Temple Within

– Exploring the sacred links of Indian dance with the Hindu temple

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The ultimate temple in India, since times ancient, has always been the human body.

To inhabit the human body is to inhabit the structure of the universe. A line of seers and sages of various communities dating back through the Vedic period and beyond, arrived at this conclusion through evolving philosophic speculations and ritualistic traditions. In the Rig Veda, one finds mention of cosmic construction as comparable to the construction of a house. But it is only in the Atharva Veda that cosmic speculation and the human body are integrated into a formal homology. Although temple Hinduism did not begin as a system of worship until the 1st century AD according to many scholars, it was nonetheless built on the foundation of all the cosmological and semantic interpretations that preceded it. Thus the Hindu temple is perceived as a link between man and God, between the earthly life and the divine life, between the actual and the ideal.

The origin of all the classical dances of India has been the Hindu temple; it is in the temple that they were conceived and nourished and it is in the temple itself that they acquired their full stature. Fostered by religion, they continue to be an intrinsic part of worship in the temples. Just as man offers flowers to God, so is dance offered as one of the truest and most beautiful creative expressions of the human spirit that serves as a means to unite with God himself.

Indian dance is not an art by itself, it is a synthesis of all arts finding a unique expression through the body. For it is in dance that ‘a painter sees beauty of line and colour, the sculptor sees the grace and the form, the actor sees the portrayal of life, and the musician and poet alike see the very embodiment of poetry in motion. Thus, with all these blended in one dedicated body and soul, the dancer herself becomes the very expression of Nataraja, the greatest Yogi of all yogis, of whom it is described that His Angika or the movement of His limbs is the world around, the Vachika, the poetry of His dance, is the language within all

speech, the Aharya, His costume and jewellery, are the moon and the stars, while the Satvika, the true expression, is the essence of Being, Shiva Himself. In Him is all united and in Him is all transcended by the divine spirit' (Rukmini Devi Arundale). This forms the very essence of Indian dance, that which encompasses within its many folds the history, the philosophy, the religion, the art and architecture of the Hindu temple, which again has been a reflection of the historical, philosophical, spiritual and artistic elements of India and her people through the centuries.

“Everything is governed by one law. A human being is a microcosmos, that is, the laws prevailing in the cosmos also operate in the minutest space of the human being”

Hindu temples take their cue from the structure of the human body itself. The vast Hindu canonical literature on Devalaya Vastu and sacred geography describe the temple as a cosmic man, the 'Purusha'. Legend has it that Vastu Purusha having blocked the Heaven from the Earth, Lord Brahma along with other gods trapped him to the ground. The ancient Indian text on Vastu Shastra (traditional science of architecture), the Mayamatam, refers the Vastu Purusha as the presiding deity of all land structures meant for temple or house. The ground plan, the Vastu Purusha Mandala is the metaphysical plan of the temple incorporating the course of heavenly bodies and supernatural forces.

The name Vastu Purusha Mandala essentially consists of three parts – Vastu, Purusha and Mandala. Stella Kramrisch, in her monumental work and certainly one of the most authoritative on Hindu temple architecture, **THE HINDU TEMPLE**, explains these thus –

Vastu is the extent of Existence in its ordered state and is likened to the Purusha, the Supernal or Cosmic Man, whose image is congruous and identical to the planned site.

Purusha, the Cosmic Man, is the origin and source of Existence (Aparaa-prakriti) and is known to the world as the manifested aspect of Himself, the Paraa-prakriti, the immutable Supreme One. In his identity with the plan, Purusha is shown in his conditioned aspect.

While Mandala, in general, denotes any closed polygon, the Vastupurushamandala specifically is a square which is its essential form. It could also be converted into a triangle, hexagon, octagon and circle of equal

area and still retain its symbolism. However, because it is the perfect shape, the square is sacred in the hierarchy of Indian architectural symbolism and is of greater significance than the circle or other forms.

This square form of the Vastupurushamandala is divided into 64 metaphysical grids or pada for the temple in which the Vastu Purusha is visualised as lying with his face, chest and stomach touching the ground, his head is at Ishanaya or north east corner of the square, while his feet are at Nairutya or south west corner. The centre of the square, the Brahmasthaana, is the vital energy point at which Lord Brahma presides over the temple site and protects it. Thus the saying 'Aham Brahmaasmi' mentioned in Brihadaranyaka Upanishad of Yajur Veda meaning 'I am Brahman. I am part of the Universe' is symbolised by the human body as also the temple, for, while the latter represents the macrocosm of the Universe, the microcosm is represented by the human body.

“The vastu-purusha-mandala represents the manifest form of the Cosmic Being; upon which the temple is built and in whom the temple rests. The temple is situated in Him, comes from Him, and is a manifestation of Him. The vastu-purusha-mandala is both the body of the Cosmic Being and a bodily device by which those who have the requisite knowledge attain the best results in temple building.” (Stella Kramrisch,; *The Hindu Temple*, Vol. I)

Describing it as the magic diagram (yantra) and the form (rupa) of the Vastupurusha, Kamrisch further elaborates,

“It is his body (sharira) and a bodily device (sharira yantra) by which those who have the requisite knowledge attain the best results in temple building, It is laid out in tabular notation as man (naraprastara) and site (vaastuprastara).

In the Purusha, Supernal man, the Supreme Principle is beheld. Beyond form and non-contingent, it is beyond description. It is known by intellectual intuition as residing in man, the microcosm, and in the universe, the macrocosm. Either is its place of manifestation. Man and Universe are equivalent in this their indwelling centre. Of this equivalence the Purusha is an image. In the Purusha, the relation of the Supreme Principle (Brahman) and of manifestation is seen as coterminous.....It is the site indwelt, and pervaded by the Purusha.....By its impress that piece of land, freed of all associations acts as primordial, undifferentiated substance (Prakriti).”

The Sangeet Ratnakara of Shaarangdeva, an authoritative treatise on Indian music indicates that the atma or Brahman creates the universe with five elements and mentioning the presence of the rope-like, serpent-like energy, the Kundalini, which has the power of creation, states that the entire world including gana, gita, vadya and nritta are based on the Nada or the Eternal Sound and that a trace of this Nada is embedded in the pindum or foetus in the mother's womb. It is indeed very significant that the Garbha Griha, the sanctum sanctorum, the most important section of the temple, also symbolises the mother's womb wherein rests the 'praana' or the life of creation in the God's image as the pindum, the very source of Nada.

This primordial energy, the Kundalini Shakti, that lies dormant in the human body, is cosmic in nature which, when awakened, ascends through the vital energy centres in the body or the chakras to ultimately unite with Shiva, the pure consciousness pervading the whole universe. Similarly, the temple representing the subtle human body with the seven psychic energy centres or chakras ultimately leads to the union of Shakti and Shiva through the awakening of pure knowledge in the minds of true seekers.

Hindu Temple and the Structure of Human Body: Comparison

In the Vastu Purusha Mandala, the seven chakras and their specific locations energise the temple structure in various ways –

1. Muladhara Chakra located at the base of the spine in the coccygeal region of the human body, finds place in the South West or Nauritya of the

- Mandala, is governed by the Asura or Demon and influences protection, strength and stability of the temple
2. Swadhishtana at the sacrum of the human, finds place in the South and in the West of the Mandala and is governed by Lord Varuna, lord of water or rain. Accordingly, creation of temple tank or water bodies in the West will influence reputation, fame, prosperity and success
 3. Manipura at the digestive glands of the human signifies the energy of fire. Represented by the navel, womb and umbilical chord in the female, in the Mandala Manipura is the energy point ruled by Lord Brahma visualised as seated on a lotus flower base. Thus navel connects Brahman with Jiva. It is to be left open and unoccupied. The central portion of the temple is to be kept open allowing the vital energy to flow unimpeded. It is believed that Vastu Purusha breaths through this open area.
 4. Anahata located in the chest or heart region of the human, is ruled by Lord Vaayu in the Mandala, relates to air and circulation of air and as the lung region of the Vastu Purusha, it should be airy
 5. Vishuddhi near the throat of the human, is the chakra from where sound emerges and reverberates in the space. In the Mandala, This point is ruled by Lord Shiva in Ishanya form and represents the space or Akaasha. Mantras chanted in this part of the temple will reverberate in space and foster balance in power
 6. Agnya situated in the forehead between the eyebrows of the human is the point where the two side nadis 'Ida' (yoga) and 'Pingala' are terminating and merge with the central channel 'Sushumna'. As per Vastu Mandala this direction is also related to open spaces ('Akasha') and to the North East corner (Ishanya). The sanctum (Garbagriha or womb chamber) is recommended at this grid, the seat of the divinity
 7. Sahasrara situated in the limbic area in the crown of the head of the human, is pure consciousness symbolised by a lotus with thousand petals. According to Vastu Mandala, while Agnya is the sanctum, the *vimanam* and *shikara* forms the space element and the currents of life ascend through the '*Brahma-randra shila*' or stone slab placed at '*griva*' (neck) of the vimana. The finial of the shikara of the vimana is the grid at which unseen sahasrara is located.

It would perhaps be apt to quote the well known Sanskrit shloka from the "Viswakarmyam Vastu Shastra" here:

*"Garba Gruha Sirahapoktam antaraalam Galamthatha
Ardha Mandapam Hridayasthanam Kuchisthanam Mandapomahan
Medhrasthaneshu Dwajasthambam Praakaram Janjuangeecha
Gopuram Paadayosketha Paadasya Angula Pokthaha
Gopuram Sthupasthatha Yevam Devaalayam angamuchyathe"*

In other words, Garbhagriham (main sanctum) is equated with human head; antarala (vestibule) is equated with human neck; ardha-mandapam (semi-hall) is compared with human chest; maha-mandapam (main hall) is equated with the stomach; flag-post is viewed along with human male organ; and gopuram or temple gateway tower is viewed along with human feet.

Upon analysing the components of classical Indian dance and music, one recognises that the svaras, the raagas and the syllabic sounds possess the potential to awaken the metaphysical or the subtle body of not only the dancer but also the sahrdaya, sensitive spectator, leading both to experience the pleasure of actually performing and witnessing the performance respectively.

As the footwork synchronises with the musical notes, and the body movements and histrionic expression blend into the raga, the sangatis (a particular variation of a phrase in a song) and gamakas (oscillation of a note, a deliberate decoration to add grace and beauty) are also intricately woven into the body movements. The lines, angles, spatial patterns and rhythm of the dance movements, all in accordance with the taala of the music, echo the universal rhythm. Specific ragas, and specific syllables and svaras or notes evoke particular moods. Every raga, defined by the arrangement of svaras in ascending and descending order, acquires a distinctive character and mood. Sets of notes with defined relationships to one another are known to be associated with the various chakras and impact them positively thereby awakening the inherent representative characters of the chakras in both the performer and the spectator.

Research conducted to analyse the impact of music on the subtle human body reveals the definite association of the chakras to the corresponding specific Bija Mantras, raagas and svaras as presented in the following table –

CHAKRAS	Bija Mantras	Svaras	Raagas
Muladhara	Lam	Shadja (Saa)	Hindol, Shyamkalyan
Svadhishthana	Vam	Komal Rishabh (re) Shuddha Rishabh (Re)	Hamsadhwani, Gurjari Todi, Yaman
Manipura	Ram	Komal Gandhaar (ga) Shiddha Gandhaar (Ga)	Abhogi, Bhimpalas, Bahtiyaar, Bibhaas, Lalit, Gunakali
Anahata	Yam	Shuddha Madhyam (Ma) Teevra Madhyam (*Ma)	Bhairav, Ahir Bhairav, Durga
Vishuddhi	Ham	Pancham (Pa)	Jayjayanti, Des
Agnya	Ksham	Komal Dhaivat (dha) Shuddha Dhaivat (Dha)	Bageshri, Bhup
Sahasrara		Komal Nishaad (ni) Shuddha Nishaad (Ni)	Durbari, Bhairavi

Emotion is said to be generated by the raagas constituted of particular svara structures which in turn are embellished further by the gamakas with their varying pitch, timbre and volume. These ragas with their constituent svaras possess the ability to influence the metaphysical apparatus of the human body while simultaneously adorning the execution of dance movements. And because music is of prime importance in the context of Indian classical dance, the dancer through her body elaborates the meaning of the words being sung and expands on their myriad connotations and deeper undertones. In the highest form of expression, the dancer sings with her body.

According to the Tamil Saint Tirumular, “our body is a temple”. And just as a temple requires the expertise of a Sthapaka for the correct planning and execution in its construction, so also in dance, does the shishya require the vigilant guidance of such a knowledgeable Guru who, with the correct training, would mould her body and mind into the perfect vehicle for delivering the art in its truest form.

Of the Sthapaka, the architect-priest who is to have the qualification of an *Acharya*, the one who knows the essence of the sacred texts – the Vedas and Agamas, Stella Kamrisch says,

“The architect of the temple was not only a master of the ‘ocean of the science of architecture’. Balanced in body and mind, he had to be versed in the traditional science (shastra) in its various branches, and as much in the

knowledge of rhythms (chhandas), mathematics and astronomy as in the conditions of different places, etc (*Samaraanganasutradhaara* – a treatise on architecture). The various arts and sciences had to be known for one and same purpose, so that he could apply in his work which was to be an image and reconstitution of the universe.”

The practice of Indian classical dance, like meditation, is understood to tame and purify the external Sthula-Sharira (the body composed of fluid, with humours and saps, as also of the bones, muscles and vital vulnerable junctures) as it quiets and balances the body’s three humours (tridosha, tridhaatu) – wind (vata), phlegm (kapha) and fire (pitta). Eventually the dancer should begin to discover the Sukhma Sharira (the subtle, metaphysical interior body) within her which articulates the psycho-spiritual experiences similar to those of the yogi and the pilgrim or devotee visiting the temple. This subtle body, most often identified with Kundalini Yoga, is defined by one of the many scholars as “ an invisible mandala formed by a combination of symbolic (but also very real) geometric figures” and often depicted as a microcosm of the universe, with the Shiva Samhita noting, “All the beings that exist in the three worlds are also to be found in the subtle body”. Rightly, it is called the seat of the Atma or soul. And the discovery of this subtle body is made possible by the awakening of the vital Kundalini energy within the dancer’s body through long-term continuous dance practice, akin to yoga. This finds a very apt expression in the Shiva Samhita –

“where the Cosmic Energy – the aggregate of all Kundalinis – resides in in separable union with Parama Shiva (Brahman, the Supreme Reality), and there merging her with the Cosmic Energy, the yogin is able to obtain spiritual release from the bondage of this world and everything worldly.....the yogin’s conscious identification of his self with his gross physical body ceases”

While the dancer herself is required to be completely immersed in rigorous practice, it is only under the tutelage of such an Acharya or Guru, as Stella Kramrisch describes, that she truly blossoms. The process of teaching is a complex, interactive exchange in which the Guru continuously reads and re-reads the signs of the shishya’s progress in each movement, in each form. The ‘inner life’ of each movement is assumed to be already present as the seed of the form, implanted by the Guru during each first lesson. In due time, training and careful correction nurtures this seed, helps it sprout and grow. The shishya gradually discovers the correct form, and its application and through continuous

practice brings its benefits to their maximum efficiency. As the Bhagavad Gita tells us, “He who attains perfection through the practice of yoga discovers of his own accord, with time, the Brahman present in his soul”.

And the role of the Guru, much like the Sthapaka of the temple, is pivotal in bringing about this realisation to the dancer, for she is guided not only in the intricacies of the dance but also in the diverse complexities existing in the experiences of human life, such that her dance also reflects life itself in its myriad moods and expressions. Her dance then becomes a flawless combination of poetry, music, movement, technique and grammar and the sattva leading to the creation of aesthetic pleasure of the highest order. Only when her dance reaches such a state of perfection that she forgets her dance body, unlearns her dance only to find her own dance, her individual kinaesthetic expression. It is only then, that she truly realises and lives the philosophy behind the dance which has been so beautifully and aesthetically put forward by the great Balasawati, the doyenne of Indian dance. Likening the structure of a Bharatnatyam recital to the structure of a temple, she states that one enters the Gopuram or outer hall of Alarippu, crosses the Ardha Mandapam or semi hall of Jatiswaram, then the Mandapa or the great hall of Shabdham, enters the holy precinct of the Deity in Varnam, into the sanctum sanctorum of Padam, from its external precinct, to the final burning of camphor accompanied by a measure of din and bustle in the concluding Tillana.

Thus the dancer, much as the devotee entering the Hindu temple, also yearns for union with the Supreme Reality through her dance, which eventually aims to liberate her soul, attaining Moksha.

Ultimately, the dancer’s body, while in the dance, becomes the sacred temple itself.

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